

Synthesis of quaternary salts of ammonia from cinnamic acids and their plant growth retardant activity

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Abstract : A series of *N,N*-dimethyl-*N*-benzyl ammonium chloride cinnamides (**1a-e**) were prepared from the reaction between cinnamyl chlorides (**4a-e**) and *N,N*-dimethylphenylmethanamines (**6a-e**). These salts were tested for their biological activity on germination, seedling growth and adventitious root formation on hypocotyl cuttings of *Vigna radiata* (SML-668) and were found to be markedly inhibit germination and seedling growth of mungbean seeds under laboratory conditions.

Keywords : Quaternary salts, cinnamic acid, plant growth retardant.

Plant growth retardants are diverse group of chemicals, which have common physiological effect on reducing stem growth by inhibiting cell division of subepical meristem^{1,2}. These have been used for many years to manipulate the size, shape and overall quality of floricultural crops, as chemical mowing agents on turf grass, to control lodging in the cereal crops etc. Quaternary ammonium salt is usually called as Quat, which is highly reactive and generates nitrogen cation in water. Nitrogen cation is lipophilic and surface active³.

In general, all the quaternary salts of ammonia (**1a-e**) prepared are insoluble in a polar organic solvents and therefore stirred with dry ether to remove any unreacted tertiary amines (**6a-e**) and acid chlorides (**4a-e**) and then preserved in vacuum desiccator. They are hygroscopic in nature and thus their spectral studies could not be done.

Chart 1

Biological activity :

The biological activity of quaternary salts of ammonia containing cinnamic acid moiety (**1a-e**) was tested using seed germination assay. Seeds of *Vigna radiata* (SML-668) were used for these studies. The effect of different concentrations of these salts was studied on percent germination and seedling growth in terms of root length, shoot length and changes in fresh and dry mass of root shoot. Germination of mungbean was reduced by all the salts at all the concentrations (Table 1) and no germination was observed by compound **1a** at 400 and 500 mg ml⁻¹

Table 1. Effect of different concentrations of various quaternary salts of ammonia on germination (%) *Vigna radiata* (SML-668) seeds

Compd.	Concentrations (µg ml ⁻¹)				
	0	10	50	100	500
Control (H ₂ O)	88	-	-	-	-
1a		53	60	60	-
1b		60	67	67	60
1c		67	60	60	60
1d		60	60	60	60
1e		50	60	60	67
3b^a		60	60	57	50

^a3-(2,4-Dichlorophenyl)prop-2-en-1-oic acid.

concentrations. The magnitude of inhibition of these compounds at higher concentrations was almost comparable with the effect of parent compound (**3b**). Table 2 shows the effect of different compounds on the length

Note

Table 2. Effect of different concentrations of various quaternary salts of ammonia on root length (shoot length) in cm of the seedling of *Vigna radiata* (SML-668)

Compd.	Concentrations ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)				
	0	10	50	100	500
Water (Control)	4.9±0.8	-	-	-	-
1a		3.9±0.2	3.2±0.4	2.8±0.3	0
1b		5.5±0.2	4.5±0.3	4.2±0.3	1.2±0.2
1c		4.4±0.9	3.9±0.3	3.6±0.2	1.0±0.3
1d		4.9±0.3	4.0±0.4	3.7±0.2	1.9±0.3
1e		4.0±0.3	3.7±0.3	3.6±0.2	2.5±0.3
3b		11±0.2	9±0.3	8.3±0.2	2.3±0.2

of root and shoot after 7 days of germination. The magnitude of inhibition of root and shoot growth increased with increasing concentrations of tested compounds. Like seedling growth, tested chemicals also affected the accumulation of seedling fresh and dry mass (Table 3).

Table 3. Effect of different concentrations of various quaternary salts of ammonia on fresh root weight (fresh shoot weight) in mg on seedling of *Vigna radiata* (SML-668)

Compd.	Concentrations ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)				
	0	10	50	100	500
Water (Control)	0.054 (0.180)	-	-	-	-
1a		0.0784	0.070	0.066	0
1b		0.070	0.051	0.047	0.03
1c		0.089	0.084	0.064	0.059
1d		0.12	0.11	0.10	0.06
1e		0.125	0.102	0.098	0.068

The root fresh weight increased in response to 10–50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentrations of all the compounds whereas fresh weight of shoot increased in response to 10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration of compound **1b**. Table 4 shows the effect of different compounds on dry mass of root and shoot. The extent of dry mass accumulation in root and shoot varied with the chemical and tested concentration.

In the present investigation different quaternary salts derived from cinnamic acids have been found to markedly inhibit germination and seedling growth of mungbean seed under laboratory conditions. The parent compound 3-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)prop-2-en-1-oic acid (**3b**) is also reported to inhibit these processes.

Experimental

Boiling points are uncorrected. Unless otherwise stated

Table 4. Effect of different concentrations of various quaternary salts of ammonia on dry weight of roots (dry weight of roots) in mg on seedling of *Vigna radiata* (SML-668)

Compd.	Concentrations ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)				
	0	10	50	100	500
Water (Control)	0.0032 (0.0078)	-	-	-	-
1a		0.009	0.007	0.006	-
1b		0.017	0.016	0.016	0.013
1c		0.005	0.004	0.003	0.001
1d		0.019	0.019	0.018	0.012
1e		0.019	0.018	0.018	0.016

all organic extract were dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and purity of analytical samples was checked by TLC. PMR spectra (90 MHz) were recorded in CCl_4 in EM 360/390 NMR spectrometer. IR spectra (thin film) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 infrared spectrophotometer (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}).

3-(2,4-Dichlorophenyl)prop-2-en-1-oyl chloride (4b) : A mixture of 2,4-dichlorobenzaldehyde (**2b**; 2.8 g, 0.016 mol), malonic acid (3.1 g, 0.03 mol), pyridine (8 ml) and piperidine (2-3 drops) was refluxed for 1 h. It was cooled and poured into excess of dil. hydrochloric acid (20%, 50 ml). The precipitates thus formed were filtered, washed with water and dried to give unsaturated acid, 3-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)prop-2-en-1-oic acid (**3b**). It gave positive alkaline KMnO_4 and sodium bicarbonate test; yield 2.8 g (80%), m.p. 236–238° (lit. 239–240.5°, E-isomer).

To the acid (**3b**; 2.17 g, 0.01 mol), thionyl chloride (1.8 g, 0.915 mol) was added dropwise and reaction mixture was refluxed with stirring for 30 min on the water bath. Excess of thionylchloride was distilled off and residue was recrystallized from dry benzene to give 3-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)prop-2-en-1-oyl chloride (**4b**); yield 1.5 g (65%), m.p. 212–213°; ν_{max} 3055, 2987, 1705, 1421, 1265, 896 cm^{-1} ; δ 6.5 (1H, d, *J* 17 Hz), 8.0 (1H, d, *J* 17 Hz), 7.2–7.7 (3H, Ar-H).

The compounds **4a** and **4c-e** were prepared similarly from benzaldehyde (**2a**), 2-nitrobenzaldehyde (**2e**); 3,4,5-trimethoxy benzaldehyde (**2d**) and 4-chlorobenzaldehyde (**2e**). The characteristic data of acids **3a** and **3c-e** is : **3a**, yield (94%), m.p. 236–237° (lit. m.p. 239–240.5°, E-isomer); **3c**, yield (86%), m.p. 238–239° (lit. m.p. 240–241°, E-isomer); **3d**, yield (80%), m.p. 123–124° (lit. m.p. 124–126°); **3e**, yield (90%), m.p. 250–252° (lit. m.p. 249–251°, E-isomer). The characteristic data of acid chlorides (**4a** and **4c-e**) is : **4a**, yield (47%), m.p. 185–187°; **4c**, yield (72%), m.p. 205–206°; **4d**, yield (47%),

m.p. 110–112°; **4e**, yield (66%), m.p. 220–221°.

N,N-Dimethyl-3-nitrophenylmethanamine (**6a**) : 3-Nitrobenzaldehyde (9 g, 0.06 mol), dimethylformamide (15.3 g, 0.21 mol) and formic acid (85%, 7.2 g) were taken in a round bottom flask, fitted with a condenser and heated at 185–190° for 6 h on an oil bath. The homogeneous solution was added drop wise to a separating funnel containing HCl solution (50 ml, 10%) and the aqueous amine chloride was washed twice with ether. The aqueous phase was treated with sodium hydroxide solution (30%, basic to litmus) and extracted with ether. After drying over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and removal of the solvent afforded the tertiaryamine (**6a**) as thick oil. Yield, 4.5 g (42%); ν_{\max} 3055, 2986, 2865, 2824, 2782, 1617, 1530, 1457, 1437, 1095, 896 cm⁻¹; δ 2.24 (6H, s, -N(CH₃)₂), 3.70 (2H, s, -CH₂N-), 7.7–8.3 (4H, Ar-H).

Tertiaryamines (**6c-e**) were prepared similarly from 4-chlorobenzaldehyde (**5c**), 4-nitrobenzaldehyde (**5d**) and 2-chlorobenzaldehyde (**5e**) respectively : **6c**, yield (45%); ν_{\max} 3053, 2983, 2948, 2822, 2782, 1598, 1458, 1420, 1172 and 1088 cm⁻¹; δ 2.2 (6H, s, -N(CH₃)₂), 3.4 (2H, s, -CH₂N-), 7.4 (4H, Ar-H); **6d**, yield (53%); ν_{\max} 3055, 2978, 2946, 2822, 2776, 1599, 1519, 1108 and 1014 cm⁻¹; δ 2.24 (6H, s, -N(CH₃)₂), 3.46 (2H, s, -CH₂N-), 7.2–7.5 (2H, Ar-H), 8.13–8.22 (2H, Ar-H); **6e**, yield (36%); ν_{\max} 3055, 2987, 2305, 1637, 1420, 1265, 1019, 896 and 746 cm⁻¹; δ 2.33 (6H, -N(CH₃)₂), 3.60 (2H, s, -CH₂N-), 7.0–7.5 (4H, Ar-H).

Quaternary salts (1a-e) : *General procedure* : A solution of cinnamyl chlorides (**4a-e**, 0.006 mol) in chloroform (5 ml) was added to tertiary amines (**6a-e**,

0.0033 mol) dissolved in chloroform (5 ml) under anhydrous conditions at 0–5 °C with continuous stirring. After the addition was over, the mixture was stirred for 3 h at the same temperature and then at room temperature for 1 h. Removal of the solvent followed by scratching of the residue in dry ether gave quaternary salts of ammonia as crystals (hygroscopic in nature) in 50–73% yield and stored in vacuum desiccator. The spectral studies of these salts could not be done because of the hygroscopic nature of these compounds. However, these compounds gave positive copper wire test.

Biological testing—Evaluation of plant growth retarding activities :

Quaternary salts of ammonia were tested on *Vigna radiata* (SML-668). To test the salts on mungbean, two replications were placed on a filter paper laid on a bottom of a petri dish of 9 cm diameter to which 7 ml of test solution of different concentrations (10, 25, 50, 100, 200, 300, 400, 500 mg ml⁻¹) of the compounds had been poured. Each dish was kept at 28 ± 2° for 5 days and thereafter the seed germination (%), seedling growth measured. Separate control treatment with distilled water was also recorded simultaneously.

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